

Sir John Bennett (1553-1627): and the Earliest Identified English Model of Causal Cognition

by

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Abstract:

While historians of psychology have generally traced the articulation of causal models of mind to the mid-seventeenth-century mechanistic turn associated with René Descartes and Thomas Hobbes, the devotional treatise *The Psalme of Mercy or, A Meditation vpon the 51. Psalme, by a true Penitent* by Sir John Bennett (one of Oxford University's 'Three Worthies' and a figure of notable scholarly repute), indicates that such sequential conceptions of cognition and action were already being articulated within the introspective theological literature of early-Stuart England. In this short paper, I examine Bennet's formulation of the inward progression: "to engender and produce from imagination, to assent; from assent, to delectation; from delectation, to resolution; from resolution, to execution," arguing that this appears to constitute the earliest currently identified English expression of a causal-psychological model linking thought to behaviour, thereby reframing the origins of modern cognitive theory in a devotional, rather than philosophical, context.

Body:

The passage under consideration appears on pages 92 and 93 of *The Psalme of Mercy or, A Meditation vpon the 51. Psalme, by a true Penitent* (1625)¹, written by Sir John Bennet while confined in the Fleet Prison following his impeachment from judicial office.² Within this devotional meditation Bennett outlines an inward progression:

"I was conceived in finne:] And therefore there is no finne that I am not apt and ready to conceive, yea, to engender, and produce from imagination, to assent; from assent, to delectation; from delectation, to resolution; from resolution, to execution." On p. 92, he confessed that from his "sinfull passions" and "euill affections" flow his "sinnes of action, or omission."

The text traces the process by which inward temptation issues in overt sin. Bennett sets out a sequence in which internal states (imagination, assent, delectation) generate volitional decisions (resolution) that result in outward behaviour (execution). The marginal "Aug. Confef." (For Augustine, Confessions), indicates Bennet's reliance on Augustinian psychology of temptation, though the five-stage syntax is his own elaboration, not a citation. In *Confessions* (LCL 25:374-375), Saint Augustine wrote:

"I myself was longing for this very thing, yet I was bound: not by someone else's iron chains but by my own iron will. The enemy still held sway over the exercise of my will, and from that had fashioned a chain for me and bound me in fetters. In fact, my feelings of sexual desire were formed out of the perversion of my will. While my will was in thrall to sexual desire, it grew into a habitual behavior: while I was capitulating to that habitual behavior, it grew into something I could not live without. These quite small links joined themselves together into the bond I called my chain: it was a cruel slavery that had me in shackles."³

There is no doubt that Bennett's vocabulary draws on Augustinian and Scholastic moral psychology, but his contribution is its systematic formalisation. We can see that Bennet follows the same inward progression but extends Augustine's fourfold chain of moral causation – from will to desire, habit, and necessity – into his aforementioned five part model. When examining current literature, for example, Cummings (2002) analyses how Protestant theology shaped inward religious language and selfhood, his emphasis remains on linguistic and literary change,⁴ and Killeen (2016) focuses on revealing how the religious text provided a key language of political debate and played a critical role in shaping early modern political thinking.⁵ Yet neither account identifies, within these texts, an explicitly psychological-causal model linking mental stages to behaviour in this particular way.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, by identifying and formalising a five-part sequence from imagination to execution, Sir John Bennet articulates a model of cognition that is both psychologically structured and causally progressive. This formulation precedes the well-documented mechanistic accounts of mind by Hobbes and Descartes, yet it has remained entirely overlooked in the historical narrative of cognitive theory. Bennet's devotional treatise, rooted in introspective theology, provides what may be the earliest extant English expression of a sequential model linking mental activity to behavioural outcome in this manner. By reframing cognition as a function of spiritual self-regulation, Bennet not only extended Augustine's moral psychology but also that he anticipated later philosophical developments. This challenges the prevailing view that modern cognitive theory emerged solely from philosophical or scientific discourse, suggesting instead that its conceptual roots may lie in the affective and penitential culture of early-Stuart religious thought. This is not to suggest that Bennet consciously anticipated mechanistic psychology, nor that he intended to formulate a cognitive model in the modern sense; rather, his devotional sequencing incidentally reproduced a structure that later theorists would formalise explicitly. Considering the texts obscurity, it would also be an overreach to suggest that Bennet explicitly influenced these later theorists, as there appears to be no evidence of such at this time.

Bibliography:

¹ Sir John Bennet, *The Psalme of Mercy or, A Meditation upon the 51. Psalme, by a True Penitent* (London: J. Dawson for John Williams, 1625), pp. 92–93. Digitised facsimile from Early English Books, 1475–1640, STC 1879, via Internet Archive (https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_the-psalme-of-mercy-or-b-i-or-j_1625) [accessed 7 November 2023].

² Bennet, Sir John (1552-1627), *The History of Parliament: The House of Commons 1604-1629*, ed. Andrew Thrush and John P. Ferris (Cambridge University Press, 2010) available at (https://www.historyofparliamentonline.org/volume/1604-1629/member/bennet-sir-john-1553-1627#footnoteref1_erlzl6b) [accessed 5 November 2023].

³ Augustine. *Confessions, Volume I: Books 1-8*. Translated by Carolyn J.-B. Hammond. Loeb Classical Library 26. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2014., pp. 373-374, [accessed online via Loeb Classical Library, Harvard University Press, on 8 November 2025].

⁴ Cummings, B. (2002). *The Literary Culture of the Reformation: Grammar and Grace*. Oxford University Press.

⁵ Killeen, K. (2016). *The Political Bible in Early Modern England*. Cambridge University Press.